

Gap Analysis on Interoperability of Blockchain Enabled Traceability Tools for Digital Product Passports

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Abstract — This paper investigates the challenges hindering interoperability among Digital Product Passport (DPP) platforms and proposes recommendations for a more standardised and interoperable ecosystem. DPPs are envisioned to be a key component of a circular and sustainable European economy by providing transparency throughout a product's lifecycle. The key gaps identified in this paper by surveying the current standardisation efforts, particularly when utilising blockchain technology include incompatible data formats across different platforms, lack of standardised governance frameworks for managing data updates and corrections in blockchain-based DPPs, and absence of universal certification standards for different sectors, among others. The paper introduces recommendations prepared for Standard Development Organisations (SDO) for addressing these gaps.

Keywords — *Blockchain; Digital Product Passport; Interoperability; Traceability; Standardisation.*

I. INTRODUCTION

A key component supporting the vision of sustainable and circular economy of Europe is the Digital Product Passport (DPP). It is considered as a digital representation of a product's lifecycle. This initiative, part of the **Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation**, aims to enhance transparency across product value chains by providing comprehensive information about each product's origin, materials, supply chain information, environmental impact, and disposal recommendations. The DPP is designed to close the gap between consumer demands for transparency and the current lack of reliable product lifecycle data. It is done by integrating critical details, for instance, product origin, material composition, environmental impact, and end-of-life recycling options. However, to achieve full interoperability across the diverse range of traceability tools currently in use in such platforms, a standardised approach to secure data sharing is necessary.

DPPs face significant standardisation and interoperability challenges [1] in their implementation, particularly when leveraging blockchain as a foundational technology for traceability. In the European context, initiatives such as GS1's Digital Link standard, Ariancee, and Circularise platforms, and sector-specific DPP projects such as the Battery Passport [2] and CIRPASS have demonstrated the potential benefits of DPPs. However, these efforts have also highlighted challenges, particularly the lack of uniform data standards and secure, scalable methods for information exchange across traceability systems and platforms. The need for standardisation is underscored by the involvement of the EU-funded StandICT.eu project¹, which has produced a

landscape of standards for DPP but notes critical gaps in interoperability requirements.

This research employs a comparative analysis of blockchain-enabled traceability tools [3], specifically focusing on DPPs, to identify interoperability gaps within existing standards and implementations. A comprehensive survey of initiatives from organizations such as GS1, ISO, W3C, and specific blockchain-based platforms like Circularise and Ariancee, was conducted. The analysis evaluates the extent to which these standards and platforms address DPP interoperability, particularly regarding compatibility with blockchain technologies. A comparative assessment of various DPP platforms, including GS1's Digital Link, Battery Passport, CIRPASS, Ariancee, and Circularise, was undertaken to identify potential fragmentation and inconsistencies in areas such as governance, data security, privacy, and interoperability.

Previous studies have identified interoperability challenges in DPPs and DPP platforms. However, they primarily focused on industry-specific solutions rather than a universal approach applicable across diverse application sectors. For instance, initiatives like the Battery Passport have developed certification protocols for specific products [2], but they lack a cross-sector perspective that could enable broader adoption. Similarly, GS1 standards are widely recognised for their contribution to interoperability in coordination, but these standards do not account for the specific cryptographic requirements of blockchain-enabled DPPs. The unresolved challenge is the fragmentation of these solutions, which inhibits full cross-sector interoperability. The paper advances this argument by emphasising the need for universal, scalable solutions that can bridge traditional data standards with blockchain based innovations in DPP. Despite the recognition of these challenges, no existing study provides a comprehensive framework that integrates data standards, governance, certification, and scalability into a single interoperable ecosystem for blockchain-enabled DPPs. This paper attempts to fill that gap by proposing a unified approach, which includes recommendations to the SDOs for developing universal data formats, governance models, and certification standards.

The above methodology of gap analysis is the first step towards supporting the future development of an open, secure, interoperable mechanism allowing various traceability tools relying on blockchains to interact seamlessly, thereby enhancing the utility and adoption of DPPs towards the enabler of circular economy.

¹ <https://www.standict.eu/landscape-analysis-report/landscape-digital-product-passport-standards>

II. INTEROPERABILITY GAP ANALYSIS

The gap analysis reveals six primary areas: data standards and formats, data security and privacy, governance, certification, scalability, and access control. A significant challenge arises from the incompatibility between traditional data capture formats (e.g., GS1 barcodes) and blockchain-based cryptographic formats. Data privacy and transparency present complex issues, as maintaining privacy while ensuring data accessibility across diverse DPP platforms, particularly under stringent regulations like GDPR, poses significant hurdles. Governance challenges emerge due to the inherent immutability of blockchain, making it difficult to manage updates or corrections, which are crucial for regulatory compliance. Additionally, the absence of universal certification standards hinders cross-industry interoperability, while scalability issues related to consensus mechanisms necessitate standardized approaches to efficiently handle large-scale data. The lack of granular access control and permissions management systems further limits interoperability among DPPs.

This section identifies the primary areas where gaps exist in standardisation and interoperability for traceability tools utilised within DPP frameworks, focusing on aspects such as data format compatibility, security, data governance, and scalability.

A. Heterogeneous data standards and formats

One of the major challenges in DPP interoperability lies in the diverse data standards and formats employed across existing DPP platforms. Various organisations, including GS1, ISO, and W3C, have introduced standards for data structure and communication in traceability systems. However, these standards vary significantly in their application, creating fragmented systems that lack the interoperability needed for DPP. For instance, GS1's barcode and Digital Link standards enable identification and sharing of product information. These have been widely adopted in retail and coordination but are limited by industry-specific applications and the complexity of adapting them to blockchain, which relies on unique cryptographic formats. GS1 has developed sector-specific standards (e.g., Battery Passport) that focus on traceability in the battery industry but do not fully cover other sectors' requirements. On the other hand, Blockchain-based DPPs often rely on cryptographic hash functions and distributed ledger formats that are incompatible with traditional data standards. For instance, the Circularise platform² utilises blockchain to offer end-to-end traceability in a secure manner but requires special data formats that can encapsulate cryptographic proofs and metadata specific to blockchain.

- **Example of incompatibility:** Circularise's platform uses unique "smart question" protocols to protect proprietary data while sharing only necessary information. This data cannot be easily aligned with GS1 formats without considerable modifications, limiting interoperability.
- **Key gap:** There is a lack of a universal data format

that can accommodate both traditional data capture methods (e.g., GS1 barcodes) and the cryptographic requirements of blockchain required for DPP. An interoperability mechanism is required to bridge this gap, enabling seamless integration across DPP platforms with different data standards.

- **Key insight:** To achieve interoperability, a standardized data format is needed that can bridge traditional formats like GS1 barcodes and blockchain-compatible cryptographic hashes. The format should be flexible enough to accommodate the specific requirements of different industries while ensuring traceability across the entire lifecycle.

B. Data security, privacy, and confidentiality

The sensitive nature of product lifecycle information (e.g., supply chain sources, production sources, environmental impacts) necessitates secure data management, particularly in blockchain applications where data is stored across decentralised nodes. While European regulations mandate strict data privacy and security standards, but ensuring compliance across DPP platforms is challenging, especially when dealing with distributed networks. Additionally, the pseudonymity of blockchain can be at odds with the transparency required for product traceability, as some information must be public while other data remains confidential. In other words, Blockchain's immutable nature provides security benefits but introduces challenges when complying with data protection laws.

- **Example of incompatibility:** Ariancee platform offers a blockchain-enabled platform for DPPs but uses encryption and selective sharing mechanisms to manage privacy concerns, which limits access to specific stakeholders. Such selective access mechanisms are often industry-specific, leading to difficulties in sharing data across broader DPP frameworks³.
- **Key gap:** Current DPP implementations lack standardised security protocols to control data access across platforms, particularly when sensitive data is involved. A standardised method to control data access based on user permissions while maintaining regulatory compliance (such as GDPR) remains absent.
- **Key insights:** A flexible, standardized access control and encryption protocol is needed for DPPs that satisfies GDPR requirements while maintaining blockchain's integrity and transparency.

C. Data governance and transparency

Blockchain provides decentralised data management, which is ideal for DPPs, but it complicates governance and transparency. Many blockchain systems are permissionless, which raises issues about data provenance, verification, and accountability. Additionally, blockchain's immutable nature makes it challenging to modify or remove data, a critical requirement under GDPR. The lack of governance

² <https://www.circularise.com/>

³ <https://www.arianee.com/post/digital-product-passports-guide>

mechanisms that allow updates or corrections in blockchain-based DPP implementations limits their practical use in real-world applications. Critical challenges include -

- **Data provenance and accountability:** While blockchain can log each transaction immutably, identifying responsible entities for specific actions can be difficult. Current DPP frameworks lack governance mechanisms to verify the accuracy of data entries, which impacts reliability.
- **Updatability in blockchain:** The immutability of blockchain records makes updating product data nearly impossible without creating conflicting information. For instance, Circularise's platform allows companies to selectively share information but does not provide an efficient way to update data once it is on the blockchain.

In this case, the gap analysis reveals -

- **Example of incompatibility:** The Battery Passport initiative under GS1 uses a consortium-based governance model for specific battery supply chain data but lacks a clear mechanism for managing data updates or error corrections across multiple stakeholders.
- **Key gap:** There is a lack of standardized governance frameworks that allow DPP platforms to update, correct, or delete data when required. This gap hinders the ability of DPP platforms to comply with regulatory requirements and maintain transparent data management practices.
- **Key insight:** Blockchain governance frameworks for DPPs must include mechanisms to manage data corrections and verify data integrity across decentralised nodes.

D. Certification and compliance

The diverse requirements across industries, as seen in initiatives like the Battery Passport and CIRPASS, underscore the need for sector-specific certification standards. Certification allows a DPP to meet regulatory requirements, such as **environmental, social, and governance (ESG)⁴ standards**, but the absence of uniform certification for DPP traceability tools is a barrier to broad adoption. While sector-specific standards exist, such as those used in the Battery Passport, a universal certification model would enable DPP platforms to meet ESG compliance more consistently. Certification efforts like GS1's Battery Passport illustrate the potential for such frameworks but remain industry-specific and lack a standardised approach for cross-sector applications. Key gaps and example of incompatibility include –

- **Sector-specific standards:** Industry-specific certifications (e.g., Battery Passport, CIRPASS) allow compliance within particular industries but lack cross-sectoral applicability, making it difficult for platforms to adapt their DPPs to various industries.

- **Lack of cross-industry standards:** Due to the diverse range of products and supply chains, certification efforts remain fragmented, lacking a universal protocol to certify compliance with DPP standards across different industries.

The **ProPare project** seeks to develop certification protocols for DPPs in the circular economy but is limited in scope to specific sectors, hindering universal adoption.

- **Key insights:** Universal certification standards for DPPs would enable consistent application of DPPs across industries and facilitate easier adaptation to new regulatory requirements.

E. Scalability and performance

While blockchain technology is well-suited for decentralized traceability, its scalability remains a concern, especially in supply chains that generate high data volumes. Blockchain's consensus mechanisms, like proof-of-work and proof-of-stake, can lead to delays and high energy consumption. Solutions such as **sidechains and Layer 2** frameworks have been proposed, but there is no standardized approach to implement these effectively within DPP systems.

- **Key gap:** There is a lack of standardised scalability solutions to accommodate the performance demands of DPPs using blockchain. Implementing a scalable framework with a unified approach is critical for enabling real-time data exchange across platforms and ensuring the feasibility of high-throughput applications.

F. Access control and permissions management

End-user access and permissions management is crucial for DPP interoperability, especially when dealing with a need-to-know basis for data access. Many DPP platforms lack a universal access control system, resulting in fragmented permissions management. Blockchain technology offers some built-in access control features, but these are not sufficiently granular for DPP needs, where different stakeholders may require access to varying levels of product lifecycle data.

- **Key gap:** The absence of a harmonised access control framework in DPP systems limits the granularity of permissions management, making it difficult to control who can view, edit, or audit data across different platforms.

III. COMMON REQUIREMENTS FOR CROSS PLATFORM INTEROPERABILITY OF DPPS

For DPPs to operate across different platforms and sectors, certain common requirements must be addressed. Here are the essential common requirements for both DPP systems and cross-platform interoperability identified as a part of the above gap analysis.

⁴ <https://www.aperam.com/the-digital-product-passport-the-esg-digital-twin-id-of-a-manufactured-product/>

A. Standardised data formats and taxonomies

A uniform data format and taxonomy for product information is crucial to make data understandable across different platforms. DPPs need standardised descriptors for product lifecycle stages (e.g., raw materials, production methods, supply chain information, usage, and end-of-life processes). A consistent taxonomy allows DPP systems to understand and interpret data from diverse sources in a uniform manner. For instance, GS1 standards, such as Digital Link, facilitate a common structure for product information, making it easier for companies to adopt DPPs with cross-industry compatibility.

B. Unique product identification

Each product must have a unique identifier that remains consistent across its lifecycle, regardless of the platform or region. Unique identifiers, like those provided by GS1 barcodes or blockchain-based IDs, are necessary for tracking products throughout the supply chain. These IDs need to be recognized by all interoperable platforms to prevent duplication and ensure accurate traceability. For instance, GS1's Global Trade Item Number (GTIN) or blockchain token-based identifiers can serve as unique product identifiers in interoperable DPP frameworks.

C. Data security and privacy compliance

Interoperable DPP systems must ensure data privacy and security, particularly for sensitive product and supply chain information, while maintaining compliance with regulations like GDPR. Secure and privacy-compliant data sharing is essential to protect intellectual property and personal data in DPPs. Interoperable DPP systems must establish encryption protocols, access control, and anonymization techniques to safeguard data while adhering to legal standards. At present, Blockchain-based DPPs often use pseudonymization and selective disclosure techniques to share necessary data without exposing sensitive information.

D. Robust access control and permissions management

Access control mechanisms that allow different stakeholders to access specific data on a need-to-know basis. In an interoperable DPP ecosystem, various actors, including manufacturers, suppliers, regulators, and consumers, will need various levels of data access. A robust access control system ensures that sensitive data is only accessible to authorised parties. For example, permissioned blockchain models or role-based access control systems (RBAC) can allow differentiated access based on user roles in cross-platform DPPs.

E. Interoperable communication protocol

Standardised communication protocols enable seamless data exchange across different DPP platforms. Communication protocols ensure that DPP platforms can send and receive data in formats that each platform can process. Protocols must support real-time data exchange to maintain up-to-date product lifecycle information across interconnected systems. APIs that follow RESTful or GraphQL standards, as well as blockchain interoperability

protocols like Interledger or Polkadot, can facilitate data exchange between DPP systems.

F. Compatibility with Blockchain and Non-Blockchain Systems

The ability to operate across blockchain-based and traditional database systems, ensuring data can flow seamlessly regardless of the underlying technology. Many DPPs use blockchain for immutability and traceability, while others rely on non-blockchain databases. Interoperable DPPs need to bridge these technological differences by adopting hybrid models or developing translation layers between systems. For example, A middleware that translates blockchain-based product data into traditional formats (or vice versa) would allow both blockchain and non-blockchain systems to participate in DPPs.

G. Certification and compliance verifications

Standardized certification to validate that DPP platforms and their data meet regulatory and industry-specific standards. Cross-platform DPPs need mechanisms to validate compliance with regulations (e.g., ESG, REACH) and sector-specific standards. A consistent certification framework can ensure that DPPs meet uniform quality and regulatory criteria across platforms. The Battery Passport initiative provides industry-specific standards for batteries, but cross-sector DPPs require a broader certification framework for interoperability.

H. Data integrity and traceability

DPPs must maintain accurate, immutable records of a product's lifecycle that cannot be tampered with or manipulated. Data integrity is essential for trust in DPP systems. Interoperable DPPs should have mechanisms to verify the accuracy of records, either through blockchain's immutability or through verifiable audit trails in centralized systems. Blockchain's append-only nature is particularly well-suited to ensure data integrity across different DPP platforms.

I. Scalability and performance optimisation

Interoperable DPP systems should be able to handle large-scale data transactions and user interactions without performance degradation. As DPP adoption scales, platforms must accommodate increasing data volumes and queries from multiple stakeholders. Scalability solutions, such as Layer 2 blockchain protocols or cloud-based scaling, ensure that DPP systems remain responsive under high loads. Layer 2 blockchain solutions, like sidechains or roll-ups, enhance scalability in blockchain-based DPPs by processing transactions off-chain and recording summaries on the main blockchain.

J. Governance and accountability mechanisms

A standardised governance model that provides accountability for data accuracy and access in DPP systems. In an interoperable DPP environment, multiple stakeholders participate, requiring a governance model to ensure that data is accurate and accessible only to authorized parties. Governance models should outline roles, responsibilities, and accountability for data management across platforms. A

multi-signature governance model or a consortium-based model where stakeholders vote on key changes can enhance accountability in DPP systems.

IV. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR INTEROPERABILITY AND STANDARDISATION

This paper makes following recommendations to address these gaps to the standard development organisation working groups. These recommendations are also derived from systematic analysis of state-of-the-art, best practices, and existing initiatives.

- **Development of a harmonised, universal data format:** To facilitate interoperability, it proposes standardising a connector that bridges traditional GS1 barcodes with blockchain-specific data formats. Such a harmonized format will allow traceability tools to operate seamlessly across DPP platforms. Developing a middleware solution that can translate data between traditional and blockchain formats, or creating a hybrid data format, could alleviate incompatibility issues and simplify cross DPP platform data sharing. It is strongly supported in [3] which highlights the importance of unified data formats for interoperability in DPP.
- **Standardised security protocols:** This paper proposes prioritising establishment of security protocols tailored for DPP systems, including privacy compliant data access controls and advanced encryption standards that work with blockchain. The proposal includes recommendation for developing a standard encryption framework and access protocol that defines how sensitive data should be stored, shared, and deleted in blockchain-based DPPs, ensuring compliance with GDPR and other data privacy regulations. The Ariane platform's selective data-sharing approach and Circularise's "smart question" protocols are good examples of industry efforts to address data privacy; however, their limitations in cross-sector implementation highlight the need for standardized security protocols. Similar issues have been discussed in [4] which emphasise privacy and secure data handling as foundational for a circular economy using DPPs.
- **Blockchain governance framework:** It is recommended to introduce a flexible data governance model, where updates and deletions are permitted without compromising blockchain's integrity, would enhance DPP compliance with European regulatory standards. This paper also proposes a decentralised governance model that provides accountability while allowing for data updates, using "multi-signature" approval models or permissioned blockchains that allow selective editing of data entries. Furthermore, it emphasises that blockchain-based DPP systems need adaptive governance mechanisms to allow for corrections and

accountability, supporting the argument for introducing governance frameworks for managing data corrections in DPP platforms [6].

- **Cross-sector certification standards:** It recommends contributing to the development of certification standards applicable across industries, creating a unified certification that verifies DPP compliance with European regulatory requirements for interoperability and sustainability⁵ which has been supported in [2]. Furthermore, advancing cross-sector certification protocols that cover universal traceability standards, ESG compliance, and sector-specific requirements are strongly recommended for creating a more adaptable and compliant DPP ecosystem in Europe.
- **Scalable solutions:** By integrating with scalable solutions such as Layer 2 frameworks, it proposes implementing a standardised approach that accommodates high data throughput for DPP platforms. This has been highly recommended in [5].
- **Access control mechanism:** Finally, this paper proposes creating a universal access control mechanism to manage user permissions across DPP platforms, enabling more granular control over data access following the evidence cited in [7].

V. CONCLUSION

The **gap analysis** in this paper identifies and elaborates on several specific areas that are not effectively addressed in existing literature, such as **governance**, **scalability**, and **certification** challenges in blockchain-based DPP systems. The main contribution of this paper is in highlighting novel insights into how these areas **intersect** and present a holistic barrier to interoperability. This intersectional perspective is a key differentiator of the study, as it provides a comprehensive understanding of why current solutions are insufficient for enabling a circular economy.

For DPPs to effectively support a circular and transparent economy, interoperable solutions must meet these common requirements. Addressing these needs will help create a seamless, secure, and standardized DPP ecosystem that can bridge technological and regulatory differences, enhancing traceability, compliance, and trust across industries and regions.

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